

Recursive State Machine Guided Graph Folding for Context-Free Language Reachability (Artifact)

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1 OVERVIEW

This artifact is for *Recursive State Machine Guided Graph Folding for Context-Free Language Reachability* conditionally accepted to PLDI 2023. It is packaged as a Docker image which can reproduce Tables 2–3 and generate results supporting Figures 10–13 in Section 6 (Experiment) of the paper.

Section 2 of this document provides instructions on setting up the environment and running a quick experiment to verify everything works. Section 3 provides instructions on reproducing our evaluation. Section 4 briefly introduces the source codes relevant to the experiment of our paper.

1.1 Dependencies

This artifact requires Docker (tested with version 20.10.17 on an Ubuntu 20.04 machine) and the initial instructions for loading the image and starting a container assume a UNIX shell. An AMD64/x86-64 machine is also required. As our experiment performs analysis on large programs, a platform with an 128 GB's memory is preferred (16 GB is the minimum requirement to test and run small benchmarks using script `./shortTest.sh`).

1.2 Container Layout

Within the container (Section 2.1), our tool `Gf` is in the folder `$GF_HOME` (i.e., `/root/GF`). It has the following structure (some directories irrelevant to our purposes are omitted):

```
$GF_HOME
|-- bench           # Benchmarks and scripts for our experiment
|  |-- run-aa.sh    # Script for running alias analysis
|  |-- run-vf.sh    # Script for running value-flow analysis
|  |-- shortTest.sh # Script for performing a partial experiment
|  |-- fullTest.sh  # Script for performing the full experiment
|  |-- tests        # small test cases
|  |-- benchfiles   # Benchmark files
|-- build           # Build of GF
`-- * (remainder)  # GF sources.
```

2 GETTING STARTED GUIDE

In this section, we first load the Docker image and run a container, and then perform a simple experiment to verify things work.

2.1 Environment Setup

First, we must load the Docker image and start a container. You can do it in the following way:

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```
docker load < gf.tar.gz
docker run -it gf
cd $GF_HOME
```

Now, we are in a Debian container, ready to run experiments. For convenience, some tools like vim and curl are available. All instructions should be performed within this container unless otherwise specified.

2.2 Simple Test

We will start with two scripts `$GF_HOME/bench/run-aa.sh` and `$GF_HOME/bench/run-vf.sh` to verify whether Gr is successfully set up. We put some small test cases in the folder `$GF_HOME/bench/tests/`. You can run a small test using the following instructions:

```
cd $GF_HOME/bench
./run-aa.sh tests/astar.peg && ./run-vf.sh tests/astar.vfg
```

This will perform 1 round of alias analysis on `astar.peg` and 1 round of value-flow analysis on `astar.vfg` without any graph simplification in preprocessing stage. If it prints messages on the screen like the following,


```
Running alias analysis on tests/astar.peg with ...
GraphSimpTime 0
#Edges 10274
#Nodes 4974
#PEdges 3962
AnalysisTime 0.041
VmrssInGB 0.0118637

Running valueflow analysis on tests/astar.vfg with ...
GraphSimpTime 0
#Edges 21501
#Nodes 17215
#PEdges 4445
AnalysisTime 0.395
VmrssInGB 0.152184
```

it means that Gr is successfully set up.

3 STEP-BY-STEP INSTRUCTIONS

This section details usage of the benchmarking script and how to reproduce our results and how to use this artifact for you own analysis.

3.1 Benchmarks and CFL-reachability Solvers

This artifact contains **10 open-source** benchmarking programs. They are listed as follows in alphabetical order:

```
astyle git_checkout i3 janet mruby nvim opencv_test_video psql redis-cli tmux
```

The abstract graphs (i.e., benchmarking files) of these programs are stored in the directory `$GF_HOME/bench/benchfiles/`.

In this artifact, 3 graph simplification approaches along with their combinations and the baseline are implemented. Totally **6 comparative graph simplification schemes** are listed as follows:

base - solving CFL-reachability without any graph simplification;
 gf - our graph folding;
 scc - cycle elimination for collapsing strongly-connected components;
 interdyck - interdyck graph simplification for removing non-Dyck-contributing edges;
 gf_scc - the combination of gf+scc;
 gf_scc_interdyck - the combination of gf+scc+interdyck.

3.2 Benchmarking Script

The basic benchmarking scripts `run-aa.sh` and `run-vf.sh` are for two clients alias analysis and value-flow analysis respectively. They are to be used as follows:

```
usage: ./run-aa.sh <INPUT_FILE> <GS_TYPE>
       ./run-vf.sh <INPUT_FILE> <GS_TYPE>
```

- `<INPUT_FILE>` refers to the benchmark to be analyzed. It should be one of the 10 benchmarking programs listed above;
- `<GS_TYPE>` refers to the type of graph simplification scheme, it should be empty or one of the six options listed above.

The scripts will print the results of each of them on the screen if valid instructions are input.

The benchmarking script `shortTest.sh` is to perform both alias analysis and value-flow analysis with all the 6 graph simplification schemes on the benchmarks (one or more) you selected from what we displayed above. It is to be used as follows:

```
usage: ./shortTest.sh <INPUT_FILES>
```

where `<INPUT_FILES>` refers to one or more benchmarks that you selected from what we displayed above.

Since the benchmark files are relatively large, the baseline may take a large amount of time to complete solve them. We provide an option to close the dynamic CFL-reachability solving process of our tool using the **global variable** `ONLINE_SOLVING` so that you can just focus on the result of graph simplification. When `ONLINE_SOLVING=yes`, the dynamic CFL-reachability solving is triggered; and when `ONLINE_SOLVING=no` the dynamic CFL-reachability solving is closed.

For example,

```
export ONLINE_SOLVING=no
./shortTest.sh i3 psql
```

- (1) will only run preprocessings of alias analysis and value-flow analysis on the two benchmarks `i3` and `psql` using all the 6 graph simplification schemes listed in Section 3.1, and
- (2) print on the screen two rows of the resulting tables (i.e., **Tables 2–3** and other 5 tables supporting **Figures 10–13** in Section 6 of our paper) regarding to the two benchmarks, as shown in Figure 1.

This is expected to complete within 10 minutes on a platform with a Quad-core Intel Xeon 2.10 GHz CPU and 16 GB memory. And you may see the results like Figure 1, where the values of nodes, edges and graph simplification time are consistent to what we presented in Section 6 of our paper.

Note: Our benchmark files of our experiment are stored in the folder `$GF_HOME/bench/benchfiles`. Modifying the folder may invalidate our benchmarking scripts.

3.3 Reproducing Our Results

The benchmarking script `fullTest.sh` is to perform the full experiment of our paper. Our experimental results can be reproduced by simply running

```
export ONLINE_SOLVING=yes
./fullTest.sh
```

That is, we test all the 6 graph simplification schemes for both alias analysis and value-flow analysis on all the 10 benchmarks listed in Section 3.1, and print their resulting tables on the screen when all analyses are finished.

Note:

- The analyses of large programs `git_checkout` and `tmux` may not be successful on platforms with memory less than 64 GB.
- The values runtime and memory overhead in the output tables can differ from our paper as they are relevant to the running platform.
- According to our experience, `./fullTest.sh` can take up one to two weeks to complete all analyses on a platform with an eight-core Inter Xeon 2.60 GHz and 128 GB memory (this is mainly because the baseline is quite slow).
- The results of finished analyses are temporarily collected in the folder `$GF_HOME/bench/stats/` (e.g., `$GF_HOME/bench/stats/aa/gf/astyle.txt` records the result of alias analysis on `astyle` with the graph simplification scheme `gf`). When running `./fullTest.sh`, you can observe such results by checking the `.txt` files.
- You can also terminate the benchmarking script using `Ctrl+C` and type `tabgen` to the terminal under the directory `$GF_HOME/bench/` to generate incomplete resulting tables (to obtain the results of finished analyses).

4 SOURCES

4.1 Relevant Source Code

The important source code files (among many others) are available in the following files under the directory `$GF_HOME`:

- `lib/CFLData/PEG.cpp` and `lib/CFLData/IVFG.cpp` contain the implementations of PEG for alias analysis and SVFG for value-flow analysis, respectively.
- `lib/AA/AAGraphSimp.cpp` and `lib/VFA/VFAGraphSimp.cpp` contain the allocator of graph simplification schemes and the implementation of cycle elimination.
- `lib/AA/PEGFold.cpp` and `lib/VFA/IVFGFold.cpp` contain the implementations of `Gf` for PEGs and SVFGs, respectively.
- `lib/AA/PEGInterDyck.cpp` and `lib/VFA/IVFGInterDyck.cpp` contain the implementations of the InterDyck graph simplification algorithm for PEGs and SVFGs, respectively.
- `include/AA/AliasAnalysis.h` and `include/VFA/VFAnalysis.h` contain the dynamic CFL-reachability solvers for alias analysis and value-flow analysis, respectively.
- `lib/RSM/GFPattern.cpp` contains the implementation of our graph folding principle, which is to identify the foldable node-pair patterns from the given patterns via an input RSM.

4.2 Foldable-Pattern Identifier

As addressed in Section 6.1 of our paper, the patterns of foldable node pairs are precomputed. In this tool, we use the module `fp`, which is mainly compiled from `lib/RSM/GFPattern.cpp`, to compute the foldable patterns. It is to be used as follows:

```
fp <RSM> <PATTERNS>
```

where <RSM> denotes the input RSM and <PATTERNS> denotes the input node-pair patterns.

In this artifact, we provide two examples in \$GF_HOME/tests/. By typing the following two commands into terminal,

```
fp tests/aa.rsm tests/aa.pattern
fp tests/vf.rsm tests/vf.pattern
```

we will get the following results:

```
Input patterns:
1; 1; a; abar; a; abar; abar; a;
0; 0; d,f; dbar,fbar; a; abar; dbar,fbar; d,f
0; 0; f; d; a; abar; fbar; dbar
0; 0; d; f; a; abar; dbar; fbar

Foldable patterns:
1; 1; a; abar; a; abar; abar; a;
0; 0; d,f; dbar,fbar; a; abar; dbar,fbar; d,f
```

```
Input patterns:
0; 0; a; ; a; ; ; a;
0; 0; a; a; a; ; ; ;
0; 0; call; ; a; ; ret; ret;
0; 0; a; call; a; ; call; ;
0; 0; call; call; a; a; ret; ret;

Foldable patterns:
0; 0; a; ; a; ; ; a;
0; 0; call; ; a; ; ret; ret;
0; 0; call; call; a; a; ret; ret;
```

Specifically, the input RSM should be formatted into transition rules where for each line

```
<SRC> <LABEL> <DST>
```

<SRC>, <LABEL> and <DST> denote the source state, label and target state of a transition rule. And they should be separated by tabs, i.e., '\t'.

Note: For <SRC> and <DST>, the boxes and local states must be annotated with the component state machines they reside in to eliminate ambiguity, and the boxes and local states are concatenated by commas (i.e., ',') to form a **global state**. For example, the RSM in Figure 4 of our paper is formatted into:

```
M1.n0      11      M1.n1
M1.n0      12      M1.n2
M1.n1      12      M1.n2
M1.n1      13      M1.b1,M1.n0
M1.b1,M1.n2 14      M1.n1
```

Besides, for the input RSM, you can specify initial state and accepting states at the end of the text file, using the identifier "init:" and "acpt:" at the beging of the lines, respectively. The example can be seen in the files \$GF_HOME/bench/tests/aa.rsm and \$GF_HOME/bench/tests/vf.rsm.

You can input one or more node-pair patterns in the file <PATTERNS>, where each line denoting a pattern. For a node-pair (x, y), a pattern should be in the following format:

```
<isXSrc>; <isYSrc>; <NotYX>; <NotXY>; <XY>; <YX>; <XNotY>; <YNotX>
```

where,

- <isXSrc> denotes whether x is a source, with 1 denoting “yes” and 0 denoting “no”;
- <isYSrc> denotes whether y is a source, with 1 denoting “yes” and 0 denoting “no”;
- <NotYX> denotes the labels of edges ending with x and not starting with y ;
- <NotXY> denotes the labels of edges ending with y and not starting with x ;
- <XY> denotes the labels of edges from x to y ;
- <YX> denotes the labels of edges from y to x ;
- <XNotY> denotes the labels of edges starting with x and not ending with y ;
- <YNotX> denotes the labels of edges starting with y and not ending with x .

Note: the labels of each of the above 6 groups should be separated by commas (i.e., ‘,’) and the groups should be separated by semicolons (i.e., ‘;’).

5 SOURCE AVAILABILITY

The source code of this artifact is already merged into the open-source GitHub repository <https://github.com/kisslune/POCR>.

6 ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We would like to thank the anonymous reviewers for their valuable feedback on earlier version of this artifact, which helped improve this final version.

Table 2: results of value-flow analysis and alias analysis with *no graph simplification*										
Bench.	Value-flow analysis						Alias analysis			
	#Node	#Edge	#P-Edge%	Time/s	Mem./GB	#Node	#Edge	#P-Edge%	Time/s	Mem./GB
i3	145259	212761	29.96	0.00	0.00	39894	95620	43.57	0.00	0.00
psql	157014	228604	27.43	0.00	0.00	40145	99164	44.59	0.00	0.00

Table 3: runtime of graph simplification methods						
Bench.	SVFG			PEG		
	GF	SCC	InterDyck	GF	SCC	InterDyck
i3	2.96	0.24	174.40	0.46	0.04	56.56
psql	2.99	0.37	132.35	0.22	0.04	48.01

Results of value-flow analysis and alias analysis with *GF*										
Bench.	Value-flow analysis						Alias analysis			
	#Node	#Edge	#P-Edge%	Time/s	Mem./GB	#Node	#Edge	#P-Edge%	Time/s	Mem./GB
i3	54358	106417	47.19	0.00	0.00	24990	64302	64.79	0.00	0.00
psql	57842	110611	41.97	0.00	0.00	26325	70160	63.02	0.00	0.00

Results of value-flow analysis and alias analysis with *SCC*										
Bench.	Value-flow analysis						Alias analysis			
	#Node	#Edge	#P-Edge%	Time/s	Mem./GB	#Node	#Edge	#P-Edge%	Time/s	Mem./GB
i3	142265	206136	30.92	0.00	0.00	39576	94300	44.18	0.00	0.00
psql	150720	210450	29.80	0.00	0.00	39899	98220	45.02	0.00	0.00

Results of value-flow analysis and alias analysis with *InterDyck*										
Bench.	Value-flow analysis						Alias analysis			
	#Node	#Edge	#P-Edge%	Time/s	Mem./GB	#Node	#Edge	#P-Edge%	Time/s	Mem./GB
i3	145259	181163	17.74	0.00	0.00	39894	88948	39.34	0.00	0.00
psql	157014	196847	15.72	0.00	0.00	40145	95168	42.26	0.00	0.00

Results of value-flow analysis and alias analysis with *GF+SCC*										
Bench.	Value-flow analysis						Alias analysis			
	#Node	#Edge	#P-Edge%	Time/s	Mem./GB	#Node	#Edge	#P-Edge%	Time/s	Mem./GB
i3	51625	100262	50.00	0.00	0.00	24790	63282	65.83	0.00	0.00
psql	52551	94197	49.02	0.00	0.00	26169	69604	63.53	0.00	0.00

Results of value-flow analysis and alias analysis with *GF+SCC+InterDyck*										
Bench.	Value-flow analysis						Alias analysis			
	#Node	#Edge	#P-Edge%	Time/s	Mem./GB	#Node	#Edge	#P-Edge%	Time/s	Mem./GB
i3	51625	88635	43.44	0.00	0.00	24790	57206	62.20	0.00	0.00
psql	52551	82633	41.89	0.00	0.00	26169	65984	61.53	0.00	0.00

Fig. 1